

Physics without time

Spatial reformulation of classical and relativistic physics

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Abstract

This work proposes a complete reformulation of classical mechanics and special relativity within a purely spatial framework, without any temporal variable. The variable t is systematically replaced by the light reference distance $L = N\lambda$, where N is the number of electromagnetic cycles and λ the wavelength of the reference radiation. The entire framework rests on a single fundamental property: the isotropy of light propagation in homogeneous Euclidean space — an experimental fact confirmed by the Michelson-Morley experiment.

This substitution leads to a deep restructuring of the unit system of physical quantities. Velocity becomes a dimensionless number — the motion coefficient $\beta = \frac{ds}{dL}$. Mass, momentum and energy converge to the same unit (the kilogram), revealing that they are not independent quantities but three manifestations of a single fundamental property: inertia. The factors c and c^2 that punctuate the relations of standard physics reduce to simple conversions between natural units and SI units — vestiges of the fragmentation introduced by the second into the measurement system. The seven SI base units reduce to three fundamental ones — the meter, the kilogram, and the coulomb — to which is added, not as a unit but as an irreducible scale-conversion factor between the microscopic and macroscopic levels of description, the Boltzmann constant k_B .

This dimensional simplification is not a formal artifice: it clarifies the understanding of physical models and the phenomena they describe. The relation $E^2 = m^2 + p^2$ follows from the Pythagorean theorem in Euclidean space, accessible from classical mechanics onward. The classical-to-relativistic transition reduces to an inversion of the role of L in the fundamental triangle — leg ($d^2 = L^2 + s^2$) then hypotenuse ($L^2 = d_o^2 + s^2$) — and to a single question: is the term $Nd\lambda$ in the differential element $dL = \lambda dN + Nd\lambda$ negligible or not? The factor γ becomes a ratio of distances, "time dilation" and "length contraction" turn out to be two manifestations of a single phenomenon — the modification of the reference light wavelength by the Doppler effect — and the constancy of $\beta = 1$ for light in all reference frames, postulated by Einstein in 1905, appears here as a theorem: it is the unique fixed point of the velocity composition law. The limit $\beta < 1$ for matter is a logical exclusion inherent to the nature of measurement and information in Euclidean space.

All numerical predictions of established physics are fully preserved. What changes is readability: a purely geometric description, in three-dimensional Euclidean space, where the structure of physical phenomena appears more directly than in a four-dimensional formalism mixing space and time.

Keywords: special relativity, spatial reformulation, temporal variable, light isotropy, dimensional convergence, Boltzmann constant, Euclidean space

Table of contents

Part I — Foundations and kinematics

1. Introduction and thesis
2. The pendulum problem: local facts
3. The reference variable L
4. Dimensional consistency, units and notation conventions

Part II — Classical dynamics

5. Spatial momentum
6. Newton's laws
7. The relation $E^2 = m^2 + p^2$ in the classical regime
8. Kinetic energy as a geometrical consequence
9. Work and the kinetic energy theorem
10. Dimensional convergence

Part III — Extension to the relativistic regime

11. From the classical regime to the relativistic regime
12. The relativistic fundamental triangle and the factor γ
13. The relation $E^2 = m^2 + p^2$ in the relativistic regime
14. Length contraction — the horizontal light clock
15. The spatial transformation: change of reference frame
16. Composition of velocities
17. $E = mc^2$ as a unit conversion
18. The limit $\beta < 1$: a logical exclusion

Summary table**General conclusion**

- A. What has been established
- B. What the spatial framework brings
- C. Scope, limitations and perspectives
 - Space as a physical entity
 - Implications for the unit system
 - A word for the kelvin and Boltzmann
 - The challenge of gravity

Appendices

- A. Kinematics example: free fall
- B. The gravitational case
- C. Experimental confirmation: the Michelson-Morley experiment
- D. Additional argument for the choice of the light reference
- E. Proof of the $x \leftrightarrow L$ symmetry
- F. Invariance theorem for $\beta = 1$
- G. The equivalence principle in the spatial framework
- H. Mass invariance and Newton's second law

Part I — Foundations and kinematics

1. Introduction and thesis

Classical mechanics, as formalized by Newton, rests on two fundamental entities: space and time. Space is the setting in which objects exist and move; time is the universal and absolute parameter that orders events and allows the evolution of physical systems to be described.

This conception was profoundly challenged by Einstein's special and then general theory of relativity, which showed that time is not an absolute and universal entity but depends on the state of motion and the local gravitational field of each observer. Relativity introduced the concept of **proper time**: the duration measured by a clock along its own trajectory through space. This proper time is an objective and measurable physical quantity, but it depends both on the state of motion of the clock and on the local gravitational field.

Do we have tangible arguments to justify the existence of space? The answer is yes. Space manifests itself directly to our senses: objects occupy positions in it, we can measure distances with a ruler, observe angles, travel along trajectories. Matter exists in space, interacts in space, and the geometrical properties of space — distances, directions, angles — are directly measurable.

Do we have tangible arguments to justify the existence of time? The answer is less obvious than it appears. We never measure time directly. What we measure are always physical processes: oscillations of a pendulum, vibrations of a caesium atom, rotation of the Earth, decay of a radioactive nucleus. A clock does not measure "time" — it counts oscillations. The SI definition of the second, adopted in 1967, anchors this unit precisely to a fixed hyperfine transition frequency: what we call 'one second' is nothing other than **9 192 631 770** oscillations of the caesium-133 atom — a count by official construction. Moreover, this count varies from one point in space to another depending on local conditions — which would be difficult to reconcile with a fundamental and universal entity.

In other words: space is directly observable; time is merely an interpretation that we impose on observable physical processes. We can point to a location in space; we cannot point to a "location in time" without referring to a physical event taking place there.

The thesis defended in this work is the following:

Time is not a fundamental physical entity. What we call "time" is a variable, defined from a local oscillatory motion, used as a reference for the local study of the evolution of systems and for relating phenomena occurring at distinct points in space.

This thesis takes here a concrete operational form: **systematically replacing the temporal variable t by a pure spatial variable, based on electromagnetic propagation**. The aim is not to replace established physics — whose results are fully preserved — but to offer a different reading of it, in which time disappears as a fundamental entity, in favor of a purely geometrical and spatial description of the physical world, bringing a new perspective and, we believe, a deeper understanding of physical reality.

An epistemological clarification is in order. The substitution $t \rightarrow \frac{L}{c}$ is, mathematically, a reparametrization — and any reparametrization preserves numerical results. The objection that follows is predictable: if the predictions are identical, what is the point? The answer lies in one word: **understanding**. A reparametrization does not change the numbers, but it can change what the numbers reveal. By replacing time with a distance, velocity becomes a pure number, mass, momentum and energy share the same unit (the kilogram), the relation $E^2 = m^2 + p^2$ follows from the Pythagorean theorem, and the limit $\beta < 1$ becomes a logical exclusion rather than a dynamical wall. None of this is visible in the temporal framework. This work therefore does not propose a different notation for the same physics — it proposes a different reading of the same physics, in which the structure of phenomena appears more directly.

This work relates to the fundamental results of Michelson and Morley (1887), Einstein (1905) and Minkowski (1909), and proposes a re-reading of them within a purely spatial framework.

It develops this reformulation step by step in three parts:

- **Part I — Foundations and kinematics:** the replacement of t by the spatial variable L , the redefinition of velocity, the equations of motion.
- **Part II — Classical dynamics:** the reformulation of Newton's laws, the dimensional convergence of mass, momentum and energy, the geometrical derivation of $E^2 = m^2 + p^2$.
- **Part III — Extension to the relativistic regime:** the determination of the factor γ , length contraction, the spatial transformation and the composition of velocities — all within three-dimensional Euclidean space.

2. The pendulum problem: local facts

To illustrate the distinction between time as an artifact and physical phenomena as realities, let us consider the following experiment. Two identical clocks, placed at two distinct points in space subject to different gravitational fields or moving at different velocities, oscillate at different rates. This is not an illusion: it is a real physical effect, verified experimentally with great precision, notably through the essential corrections applied to GPS systems.

Consider two identical point pendulums P_1 and P_2 . When they are located at the same point A in space, they evolve under the same local physical conditions — same gravitational field, same electromagnetic environment... Their oscillations are synchronous and indistinguishable.

Figure 1 — The pendulum problem: local synchronization, spatial desynchronization.

When P_1 remains at A and P_2 is transported to a distinct point B , the local physical conditions at A and B differ. The two pendulums become desynchronized: P_2 may complete 2 oscillations while P_1 completes 1.

The essential lesson is the following: one oscillation of P_1 at A is an absolute local fact, intrinsic to the physical properties of point A . Likewise, one oscillation of P_2 at B is an absolute local fact. These two facts cannot be directly compared: they take place in two regions of space with different local physical properties.

Desynchronization is not an effect on time. It is a direct consequence of the local properties of space at A and B . What relativity calls "time dilation" is merely the difference in counts of local physical transformations, caused by the local physical conditions of space at A and B . One never needs to invoke "time": one always invokes local physical processes and their counts.

3. The reference variable L

If time is an artifact used to count oscillations and relate two phenomena separated in space, it should be replaced by a tangible physical variable of spatial nature. Electromagnetic propagation naturally imposes itself as a universal reference process, for four fundamental reasons:

1. Light is an absolute property of space itself, independent of the source and the observer.
2. A light path is determined by the local physical properties of the space traversed.
3. It is directly measurable by counting electromagnetic cycles.
4. The conversion from the temporal framework (SI) to the spatial framework is immediate, which guarantees a simple correspondence between the two formulations.

These properties rest on two fundamental characteristics of Euclidean space: homogeneity — physical laws are invariant under translation, that is, identical at every point — and isotropy — they are invariant under rotation, that is, identical in every direction. The Michelson-Morley experiment confirmed this isotropy in a moving reference frame (the Earth), establishing that it is a property of space itself, independent of the reference frame of observation (see Appendices C and D).

Homogeneity guarantees that the wavelength λ of the reference does not vary from one point in space to another. It is within this framework that the classical reformulation is developed (Parts I and II). Part III will show that relative motion modifies the wavelength perceived by the observer — not through an inhomogeneity of space, but through the geometrical lengthening of the light path in this same homogeneous space.

Isotropy guarantees that light propagation can serve as a universal reference, regardless of direction.

The fundamental variable is thus defined as:

$$L = N\lambda$$

where N is the number of electromagnetic cycles and λ the wavelength of the reference radiation. L is a length — a pure spatial variable.

The relation to the former temporal variable is then explicit: $t = \frac{L}{c}$. This is not a definition of time: it is the recognition that what we call "time" is merely a distance divided by a conversion constant.

3.1. The differential element of L

The differential element of the distance traveled by the wavefront is written:

$$dL = \lambda dN + Nd\lambda$$

This expression contains **two terms of distinct physical nature**. The first, λdN , describes the progression of the wavefront by cycle counting at constant wavelength. The second, $Nd\lambda$, expresses the variation of the wavelength itself during propagation.

Under the usual conditions of classical mechanics — flat, uniform space, velocities much smaller than c — the wavelength λ is constant and:

$$dL = \lambda dN$$

It is within this simplified framework that the reformulation of classical physics is developed (Parts I and II).

The transition to the relativistic regime (Part III) will correspond precisely to the moment when the term $Nd\lambda$ can no longer be neglected. This term manifests itself notably in the Doppler effect, when the motion of the source modifies the wavelength perceived by the observer during propagation between source and observer.

But more fundamentally, Part III will show a different origin of $Nd\lambda$ through the light clock: it is the same light path — that of the photon inside the clock — which is perceived geometrically differently depending on the reference frame of observation, without propagation between a source and an observer. This difference in perception modifies the measurement of all physical quantities of objects in motion relative to the observer.

4. Dimensional consistency, units and notation conventions

4.1. The constant c as a conversion factor

In this new framework, every term with a temporal connotation is removed, including from the units. The constant c simply becomes a conversion factor between two equivalent units: **the second in the SI framework** and **the meter in the spatial framework**. The distance traveled by light in one second ($\approx 299\,792\,458\text{ m}$), sometimes called the **light-second**, should rather be named the **light-meter**, since it is a length — this change of name asserts that this quantity is a length, and nothing else. The entire work that follows uses the meter as the unit of length. The conversion of the reference variable to the SI framework becomes immediate: $t = \frac{L}{c}$.

4.2. Kinematic quantities

Let us define:

the position vector $\vec{r} = \overline{OM} = x.\vec{i} + y.\vec{j} + z.\vec{k}$ and the displacement vector $d\vec{r} = ds.\vec{u}$

The foundation of this reformulation is the replacement of the temporal variable $t(s)$ by the spatial variable $L(m)$. From this change follows a major consequence: velocity, now being the ratio of two quantities of the same nature (ds and dL), becomes a pure dimensionless number. It therefore receives its own symbol, the **motion coefficient**:

$\vec{\beta} = \frac{d\vec{r}}{dL}$ of magnitude $\beta = \frac{ds}{dL}$ a **dimensionless** quantity.

All other quantities retain their classical symbols. Their units change, but their physical role is identical:

— Acceleration \vec{a}_{SI} ($m \cdot s^{-2}$ in the SI framework) becomes $\vec{a} = \frac{d^2\vec{r}}{dL^2}$, expressed in m^{-1} , in accordance with the conventions of section 4.3 below.

The coefficient $\beta = \frac{ds}{dL}$ is the ratio between the distance traveled by the object and the distance traveled simultaneously by the wavefront. To say that an object exceeds c would amount to saying that $ds > dL$, that is, that the object travels a greater distance than the ruler that measures it. Section 18 will show that this limit is not a dynamical constraint imposed on matter, but a logical exclusion inherent to the very nature of measurement and information in Euclidean space.

4.3. Notation conventions

Throughout this work, all physical quantities reformulated in the spatial framework bear **the same symbols** as their counterparts in classical physics: \mathbf{a} for acceleration, \mathbf{F} for force, \mathbf{p} for momentum, $\mathbf{E}k$ for kinetic energy, \mathbf{W} for work, \mathbf{E} for total energy. Only velocity receives its own symbol — the motion coefficient β — because it is the only quantity whose mathematical nature changes fundamentally: from a dimensioned quantity ($m \cdot s^{-1}$), it becomes a pure dimensionless number.

When it is necessary to refer to quantities from the former framework for comparison or verification, these are distinguished by the subscript SI : \vec{a}_{SI} , \vec{F}_{SI} , \vec{p}_{SI} , $\mathbf{E}k_{SI}$, \mathbf{W}_{SI} . The full set of conversion relations between the two formulations is gathered in the summary table at the end of the document. **In the absence of a subscript, any quantity is expressed in the spatial framework.**

In this work, the term *spatial framework* designates the proposed reformulation, as opposed to the *temporal framework* (or *SI framework*) of standard physics. Within the spatial framework, we distinguish two regimes: the *classical regime* ($\beta \ll 1$, Parts I and II) and the *relativistic regime* ($\beta \leq 1$, Part III).

4.4. Example: gravitational acceleration

The terrestrial gravitational acceleration $g_{SI} \approx 9.81 \text{ ms}^{-2}$ becomes in the spatial framework:

$$g = \frac{g_{SI}}{c^2} \approx 1.09 \times 10^{-16} \text{ m}^{-1}$$

This value has a direct physical interpretation.

By definition, $g = \frac{d\beta}{dL}$: it is the variation of the motion coefficient β per unit distance traveled by the light wavefront. Its inverse is therefore:

$$\frac{1}{g} = \frac{dL}{d\beta}$$

This quantity is the **distance that the light wavefront must travel to change β by one unit** — that is, the light reference distance required for an object initially at rest to reach $\beta = 1$, in other words the speed of light. Let us compute this distance:

$$\frac{1}{g} \approx 9.16 \times 10^{15} \text{ m} \approx 0.97 \text{ light-year}$$

Under terrestrial gravity alone, the light wavefront would have to travel nearly one light-year before an object in free fall reached the speed of light.

Let us note that the quantity $\frac{1}{g}$ receives here, from classical physics alone reformulated in the spatial framework, an interpretation different from the one given in relativistic physics. General relativity interprets this length as a radius of curvature of spacetime — a notion that calls upon a fourth temporal dimension and a non-Euclidean geometry. In our framework, this interpretation is neither necessary nor relevant: $\frac{1}{g}$ is a **characteristic length of the light reference**, which measures the intensity of gravitational acceleration relative to electromagnetic propagation, in three-dimensional Euclidean space. This reinterpretation, more elementary and more direct, is made possible by the elimination of the temporal variable.

— See Appendix A for a kinematics example: free fall —

Part II — Classical dynamics

5. Spatial momentum

5.1. Definition

Momentum is the **manifestation of inertia along the trajectory, inertia in action** — the part of total inertia engaged in motion. The greater the momentum of a body, the harder it is to alter its trajectory (proof in section 6.4. **Momentum and trajectory deflection**).

Classical momentum is $\vec{p}_{SI} = m\vec{v}$ (in $kg\ m\ s^{-1}$). Replacing \vec{v} by $\vec{\beta}$,

$\vec{p}_{SI} = c \times m\vec{\beta} = c\vec{p}$. **Spatial momentum** is therefore:

$$\vec{p} = m\vec{\beta} \quad \text{hence} \quad \vec{p} = \frac{\vec{p}_{SI}}{c}$$

5.2. Dimensional analysis

$$[p] = [m][\beta] = kg \times 1 = kg$$

Spatial momentum is expressed in **kilograms**, in the same unit as mass. The usual distinction between mass and momentum is of purely dimensional origin: it arises from the introduction of the second. By eliminating time, this distinction disappears.

5.3. Physical interpretation

The coefficient β measures "what fraction of light" the body travels. Momentum $p = m\beta$ is therefore the part of inertia engaged in motion — zero when $\beta = 0$, and all the greater as β is large, β remaining much smaller than 1 in the classical regime: relativistic cases will be treated in Part III.

6. Newton's laws

6.1. First and third laws

The first and third laws of Newton transpose trivially into the spatial framework: the principle of inertia is stated identically with the vector $\vec{\beta}$ in place of \vec{v} , and the action-reaction principle is preserved. Only the second law requires development.

6.2. Newton's second law reformulated

The second law is classically written $\vec{F}_{SI} = m\vec{a}_{SI}$. Using the relation $\vec{a}_{SI} = c^2\vec{a}$ with a in m^{-1} :

$$\vec{F}_{SI} = mc^2\vec{a}$$

We define the **spatial force** \vec{F} as:

$$\vec{F} = m\vec{a}$$

Dimensional analysis

$$[a] = m^{-1} \Rightarrow F = \frac{F_{SI}}{c^2} \Rightarrow [F] = [m]. [a] = kg \cdot m^{-1}$$

The dimension obtained in the spatial framework — that of a linear mass density — deserves attention. In the SI framework, force reads literally as "a mass multiplied by an acceleration." This reading, although formally correct, says nothing about what a force physically *is* — it describes how it acts, not what it is. In the spatial framework, the dimension changes radically in appearance: **it expresses a potential variation of inertia per unit length traveled by the light reference.**

The role of c^2

The factor c^2 in $F_{SI} = Fc^2$ is a **conversion factor** between spatial units and SI units — the same as in $E = mc^2$.

— See Appendix B for the gravitational case —

6.3. Momentum theorem

The second law, in its most general form, becomes (see Appendix H):

$$\Sigma \vec{F}_{ext} = \frac{d\vec{p}}{dL}$$

The vector decomposition of the fundamental law, writing $\vec{p} = m\beta\vec{u}$ where \vec{u} is the unit vector tangent to the trajectory, gives:

$$\vec{F} = m \cdot \left(\left(\frac{d\beta}{dL} \right) \cdot \vec{u} + \beta \cdot \left(\frac{d\vec{u}}{dL} \right) \right)$$

The quantity $\vec{a} = \frac{\vec{F}}{m}$ — variation of the motion coefficient $\vec{\beta}$ per unit distance traveled by the light reference — measures the modification of the state of motion of the body.

- The tangential term, $\frac{d\beta}{dL}\vec{u}$, modifies the magnitude of \vec{p} — the intensity of the inertia engaged in motion. A purely tangential force (such as in vertical free fall) does not curve the trajectory. In this case, $\vec{a} = \frac{d\beta}{dL}$ and its inverse $\frac{1}{a}$ is the distance that the light wavefront must travel for the object to reach $\beta = 1$ — See Appendices A and B.
- The normal term, $\beta \frac{d\vec{u}}{dL}$, modifies the direction of \vec{p} — the orientation of this inertia in space, the trajectory curves. A purely normal force (such as for a satellite in uniform circular orbit) does not modify the magnitude of $\vec{p} = m \cdot \vec{\beta}$. In this case $\vec{a} = \beta \left| \frac{d\vec{u}}{dL} \right|$ and the force modifies the direction of the trajectory without changing the magnitude of $\vec{\beta}$.
- In the general case, the force \vec{F} modifies the motion coefficient $\vec{\beta}$ — in magnitude and in direction.

6.4. Momentum and trajectory deflection

According to Newton's second law, $\vec{F} = \frac{d\vec{p}}{dL}$, hence for a force perpendicular to the motion (β constant), $|\vec{F}| = \left| \frac{d\vec{p}}{dL} \right|$ reduces to $F = p \left| \frac{d\vec{u}}{dL} \right| \Rightarrow \left| \frac{d\vec{u}}{dL} \right| = \frac{F}{p}$

For a given force intensity F , the greater p is, the smaller $\left| \frac{d\vec{u}}{dL} \right|$, which is a measure of the trajectory deflection — becomes, meaning the less the direction of motion changes. An object with a large momentum resists trajectory deflection more strongly.

This is precisely the meaning of the expression "inertia in action": p measures the resistance to change of direction, exactly as m measures the resistance to change of the motion coefficient.

7. The relation $E^2 = m^2 + p^2$ in the classical regime

We show that this relation, known from special relativity, can be geometrically established in the classical regime.

In the following construction 7.1., the reference wavefront L is identified with the path of a light flash emitted by the object. This identification is justified in the classical regime ($\beta \ll 1$): the object being quasi-stationary during the propagation of the flash, the light path is indistinguishable from the vertical, and the distance traveled by the flash coincides with the reference distance L . This hypothesis will cease to be valid in the relativistic regime (Part III), where the light path will have to be analyzed using the light clock (section 11).

7.1. Geometrical construction: the fundamental triangle

Consider a moving object equipped with a light source, traveling horizontally with a coefficient β . An observer is located directly below the initial position of the object. At the moment when the object is directly above the observer, a light flash is emitted. Light propagates isotropically in Euclidean space; in particular, a wavefront propagates vertically downward.

While this wavefront travels the distance L vertically, the object moves a distance s horizontally. Following this displacement, the distance between the observer and the position of the object is d .

Figure 2 — *The fundamental triangle in the classical regime: $d^2 = L^2 + s^2$.*

L and s are physically orthogonal (vertical and horizontal). The Pythagorean theorem gives:

$$d^2 = L^2 + s^2$$

7.2. Transition to the inertia triangle

Dividing by L^2 :

$$\frac{d^2}{L^2} = 1 + \frac{s^2}{L^2} = 1 + \beta^2$$

Multiplying by m^2 :

$$\left(m \frac{d}{L}\right)^2 = m^2 + (m\beta)^2 = m^2 + p^2$$

Setting $E = m \frac{d}{L}$:

$$E^2 = m^2 + p^2$$

Figure 3 — *The inertia triangle in the classical regime.*

The quantity $E = m \cdot \frac{d}{L}$, defined geometrically as the hypotenuse of the inertia triangle, possesses three remarkable properties:

- it has the dimension of **mass** (in *kg*) ;
- for a body at rest ($\beta = 0$), it equals m ;
- for a body in motion ($\beta \neq 0$), it is greater than m : motion adds a contribution to it.

The difference ($E - m$), which will be identified as kinetic energy in section 8, represents the part of inertia contributed by motion. The quantity E thus encompasses both the rest mass and the energy associated with motion: this is why we call it **total mass-energy**.

7.3. Expression of E and verification

From $\frac{d}{L} = \sqrt{1 + \beta^2}$

$$E = m\sqrt{1 + \beta^2}$$

Verification: $E^2 = m^2(1 + \beta^2) = m^2 + m^2\beta^2 = m^2 + p^2$

7.4. Summary of the proof

This proof rests on three pillars, once $\beta = \frac{s}{L}$ and $p = m\beta$ are defined:

1. **The isotropy of light propagation in Euclidean space** — an experimental fact authorizing the choice of a wavefront perpendicular to the motion.
2. **The Pythagorean theorem in Euclidean space** — the mathematical framework of classical mechanics.
3. **The invariance of mass: m** is an intrinsic property of the object, identical in all reference frames.

The relation $E^2 = m^2 + p^2$ appears as a **direct geometrical consequence** of the isotropy of light propagation in Euclidean space — without any recourse to special relativity.

Note: In this construction, L is a leg of the fundamental triangle and d the hypotenuse ($d^2 = L^2 + s^2$). Part III will show that the transition to the relativistic regime precisely inverts this geometry: L becomes the hypotenuse ($L^2 = d^2 + s^2$) — and this inversion alone suffices to produce the whole of special relativity.

8. Kinetic energy as a geometrical consequence

8.1. Kinetic energy: geometrical definition

Kinetic energy is the difference between the total mass-energy and the rest mass:

$$Ek = E - m = m(\sqrt{1 + \beta^2} - 1)$$

8.2. Classical approximation

The classical regime is defined by $\beta \ll 1$. This is the **founding condition** of Newtonian mechanics.

For $\beta \ll 1$, $\sqrt{1 + \beta^2} \approx 1 + \frac{1}{2}\beta^2$, therefore:

$$Ek \approx \frac{1}{2} m\beta^2$$

The expression $\frac{1}{2} m\beta^2$ is the first-order term of the series expansion of the exact expression of Ek . The approximation is not introduced to obtain the result: it is the **very definition of the classical regime**.

8.3. Relation between kinetic energy and momentum

The fundamental relation $E^2 = m^2 + p^2$ allows kinetic energy to be expressed directly in terms of m and p .

$$E^2 - m^2 = p^2 \Rightarrow (E - m)(E + m) = p^2, \text{ and since } Ek = E - m:$$

$$Ek = \frac{p^2}{E + m}$$

This relation is **exact**. It shows that kinetic energy is entirely determined by the momentum p and the mass m , through the total mass-energy $E = \sqrt{m^2 + p^2}$.

In the classical regime ($\beta \ll 1$), $E \approx m$, hence $E + m \approx 2m$, and the relation simplifies to:

$$Ek \approx \frac{p^2}{2m}$$

Verification: $\frac{p^2}{2m} = \frac{(m\beta)^2}{2m} = \frac{1}{2}m\beta^2$, which is indeed the classical expression of kinetic energy.

The exact form $Ek = \frac{p^2}{E + m}$ and its classical approximation $Ek \approx \frac{p^2}{2m}$ confirm that kinetic energy is not an independent quantity: it follows entirely from the two fundamental quantities m and p .

8.4. The two fundamental quantities of dynamics

Kinetic energy and total mass-energy are not independent quantities: they are entirely determined by the mass m and the momentum p through the Pythagorean relation $E^2 = m^2 + p^2$. The total mass-energy is $E = \sqrt{m^2 + p^2}$, the kinetic energy is $Ek = \frac{p^2}{E + m}$.

Force acts on mass and modifies the motion coefficient $\vec{\beta}$. In doing so, it creates or modifies the momentum $\vec{p} = m\vec{\beta}$, and produces work $\delta W = \vec{F} \cdot d\vec{r}$ which results in an energy transfer ($\Delta Ek = W$). The total mass-energy $E = \sqrt{m^2 + p^2}$ adjusts accordingly.

The only two fundamental quantities of dynamics are therefore m and p . What physics calls mass and momentum are merely two manifestations of the same phenomenon: inertia.

— Mass m is inertia **at rest**; it measures the resistance to change of the motion coefficient.

— Momentum $\vec{p} = m\vec{\beta}$ is inertia **in action**: it measures the resistance to change of direction of motion.

In a reference frame where the body is at rest ($\beta = 0$), only mass m is involved: there is no momentum, hence no resistance to change of direction. In any reference frame where the body is in motion, m remains the fundamental measure of resistance to change of the motion coefficient, and $\vec{p} = m\vec{\beta}$ adds to it a specific resistance to change of direction.

9. Work and the kinetic energy theorem

9.1. Spatial work: $\delta W = \vec{F} \cdot d\vec{r}$

Classical work $\delta W_{SI} = \vec{F}_{SI} d\vec{r}$ becomes:

$$W = \frac{W_{SI}}{c^2}$$

Since $d\vec{r} = ds \cdot \vec{u}$, the component of work along the trajectory is written: $\delta W = F_t \cdot ds$

where $F_t = \vec{F} \cdot \vec{u}$ is the tangential component of the force.

Dimension: $[W] = kg \cdot m^{-1} \times m = kg$. Spatial work is homogeneous to a mass.

9.2. Kinetic energy theorem

$$\Delta Ek = W$$

Proof

$$W = \int_{s_1}^{s_2} F_t \cdot ds = \int_{s_1}^{s_2} m a_t ds \quad \text{and since} \quad ds = \beta dL, \quad a_t = \frac{d\beta}{dL}$$

$$\text{Integrating: } W = m \int_{\beta_1}^{\beta_2} \beta d\beta = \frac{1}{2} m \beta_2^2 - \frac{1}{2} m \beta_1^2 = \Delta Ek.$$

10. Dimensional convergence

The most remarkable result of the dynamics is the convergence of three fundamental quantities to the same unit:

Quantity	Spatial expression	Spatial unit	SI conversion
Mass	m	kg	m
Momentum	$p = m\beta$	kg	$p_{SI} = p \times c$
Kinetic energy	$Ek = \frac{m\beta^2}{2}$	kg	$Ek_{SI} = Ek \times c^2$

Three manifestations of inertia

This convergence reveals that mass, momentum and kinetic energy are **different manifestations of a single fundamental property: inertia**. The only thing that distinguishes them is the dimensionless coefficient β :

- m : **intrinsic** inertia (independent of motion);
- $\vec{p} = m\vec{\beta}$: inertia **in action**, engaged along the trajectory, which expresses the resistance to change of direction (vectorial);
- $Ek = \frac{m\beta^2}{2}$: inertia **in action, added to intrinsic inertia** by motion (scalar).

Note: any quantity having the dimension of an energy in the **SI** framework — work, potential energy, thermal energy, chemical energy, electrical energy, magnetic energy, electromagnetic energy — is likewise expressed in kilograms in the spatial framework, by division by c^2 . The dimensional convergence is not specific to mechanics: it is universal and concerns all forms of energy. This result moreover rejoins the mass-energy equivalence $E = mc^2$, which in our framework reads simply as a unit conversion between the kilogram and the joule.

Part III — Extension to the relativistic regime

11. From the classical regime to the relativistic regime

11.1. Preamble

In the classical regime (section 7), we used a free light flash emitted from an object passing directly above the observer. This construction rests on the hypothesis that light descends vertically towards the observer. Yet this hypothesis is justified only because $\beta \ll 1$: the object is quasi-stationary during the propagation of the flash, and the vertical of the object coincides with that of the observer.

In the relativistic regime, β is no longer negligible. The object moves significantly during the propagation of the light from the flash, and the direction of emission in the reference frame of the object no longer corresponds to the direction of reception in the reference frame of the observer. The construction of the free flash loses its geometrical justification.

All reference frames considered in this Part III are Galilean (inertial): they are in uniform rectilinear motion with respect to one another. The extension of the spatial framework to accelerated reference frames and to the gravitational field is outlined in Appendix G.

11.2. The vertical light clock

To circumvent this difficulty, we use a **specific object of study**: an object on which is mounted a device that mechanically constrains the light path, a **light clock**. It is an idealized device whose purpose is to measure the reference distance L itself — in other words, **to measure the ruler that measures**. In the proper reference frame of this object (R'), the photon travels the distance d_0 , defined as the proper distance between the two mirrors. In the reference frame of the observer (R), during the displacement s of the object, the same photon follows a longer diagonal path, which constitutes the reference distance L perceived by the observer. The comparison of the two paths reveals that the light reference is not perceived in the same way depending on the reference frame of observation — and it is this difference in perception that is the origin of all relativistic effects.

Figure 4 — The light clock in R' and R . In R , light travels the diagonal L .

Important notes:

- What interests us here is the displacement s of the physical object itself in Euclidean space. The clock is only there to make L visible.
- The distance between the mirrors is denoted d_0 (and not d as in Part II) to avoid any confusion: in section 7.1, d designated the hypotenuse of the classical triangle ($d^2 = L^2 + s^2$), whereas here d_0 is a leg of the relativistic triangle ($L^2 = d_0^2 + s^2$). The subscript 0 recalls that this is the proper distance, measured in the reference frame R' of the object.
- Once light is emitted, its trajectory becomes independent of the object and of the observer.

11.3. The role of $Nd\lambda$

We established in section 3 that the differential element of the reference variable is written $dL = \lambda dN + Nd\lambda$. All of Part I and Part II rest on the hypothesis $\lambda = \text{constant}$, that is $d\lambda = 0$ and $dL = \lambda dN$. Let us now examine what happens when this hypothesis is no longer valid.

For a light clock in motion relative to an observer. From the observer's perspective, we have seen that the photon does not follow a vertical path: it follows a diagonal trajectory, geometrically longer. The number of cycles N is an invariant (an integer count does not depend on the reference frame), but the wavelength perceived by the observer **changes**. The term $Nd\lambda$ is no longer zero.

The transition between classical physics and relativistic physics therefore comes down to a single question:

Can $Nd\lambda$ be neglected or not?

- Yes ($\beta \ll 1$): $\lambda \approx \text{constant} \rightarrow dL = \lambda dN \rightarrow \text{classical regime}$ (Parts I and II).
- No (β significant): λ varies $\rightarrow dL = \lambda dN + Nd\lambda \rightarrow \text{relativistic regime}$ (Part III).

All of relativity lies in this term. And this term has a purely spatial origin: light travels a geometrically different path when the source is in motion in three-dimensional Euclidean space — longer if the source recedes, shorter if it approaches.

12. The relativistic fundamental triangle and the factor γ

Consider the light clock, from figure 4, mounted on the moving object: a photon bounces vertically between two mirrors separated by a proper distance d_0 , measured in the reference frame R' of the object at rest.

12.1. The light clock seen from R' and R

In the reference frame R' :

The clock is at rest. Light travels d_0 vertically. No horizontal displacement: $x'_1 = x'_2$.

In the reference frame R of the observer:

The clock moves over a distance s . Light follows a diagonal trajectory L . For the observer, this diagonal is the path actually traveled by light: it is our reference variable. The vertical distance d_0 is the same (perpendicular to the motion).

Let us note that the quantity d_0 , the proper distance in R' , designates here the distance between the mirrors of the light clock (vertical leg in R). The number of cycles N being an invariant (integer count), one can write $d_0 = N\lambda'$ in R' and $L = N\lambda$ in R . Since $L > d_0$, we necessarily have $\lambda > \lambda'$: this is the direct manifestation of the term $Nd\lambda$ identified in section 11 as the hinge between the classical and relativistic regimes.

Figure 5 — The relativistic fundamental triangle: $L^2 = d_0^2 + s^2$.

The right triangle is formed by:

- d_0 : distance traveled by the wavefront in the local space of the object (R'). It is the light reference distance **proper** to R' . We have $d_0 = N\lambda'$.
- s : distance traveled simultaneously by the object in Euclidean space, measured in R . The motion coefficient is $\beta = \frac{s}{L}$.
- L : light reference distance in R . The light clock makes it visible: the internal photon, seen from R , travels this distance diagonally. We have $L = N\lambda$, with $\lambda > \lambda'$ since $L > d_0$.

Crucial difference with the classical case: in the classical case (section 7), L was a leg and d the hypotenuse ($d^2 = L^2 + s^2$). Here, L is the **hypotenuse**:

$$L^2 = d_0^2 + s^2$$

12.2. Determination of the factor γ

Starting from $L^2 = d_0^2 + s^2$, let us express d_0 in terms of L and β :

$$d_0^2 = L^2 - s^2 = L^2(1 - \beta^2)$$

$$d_0 = L\sqrt{1 - \beta^2} \quad \text{hence} \quad \frac{d_0}{L} = \sqrt{1 - \beta^2}$$

The inverse of this ratio defines the factor γ :

$$\gamma = \frac{L}{d_0} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}$$

This factor is a pure **ratio of distances in Euclidean space**: the ratio between the diagonal path L of the photon and the proper distance d_0 between the mirrors. There is no reference to any time dilation.

Note: Recall that in the classical regime (section 7), we had $d = L\sqrt{1 + \beta^2}$ — the sign difference comes precisely from the inversion of the role of L in the triangle. This parallel makes the contrast between the two regimes all the more striking.

Using the relations $d_0 = N\lambda'$ and $L = N\lambda$, where N is the number of cycles (**constant here**), this ratio also reads:

$$\gamma = \frac{L}{d_0} = \frac{N\lambda}{N\lambda'} = \frac{\lambda}{\lambda'}$$

The factor γ is therefore also the ratio between the wavelength perceived in R and the proper wavelength in R' . It is a **dilation of the wavelength** of the light reference, a direct geometrical consequence of the diagonal lengthening of the light path in Euclidean space. What traditional physics interprets as a "time dilation" turns out to be, in the spatial framework, a dilation of the wavelength of the light reference.

12.3. The "slowing down" of R' processes as perceived in R

When the light reference perceived in R travels L , the light of the light clock progresses only by $d_0 = \frac{L}{\gamma}$ in R' . The local processes in R' "advance more slowly" — not because time slows down, but because **the light path, perceived in R , is geometrically longer in Euclidean space**. The complete interpretation of this result will be developed in section 14.3, where it will be unified with length contraction.

13. The relation $E^2 = m^2 + p^2$ in the relativistic regime

Dividing $L^2 = d_0^2 + s^2$ by d_0^2 :

$$\frac{L^2}{d_0^2} = 1 + \frac{s^2}{d_0^2}$$

Multiplying by m^2 :

$$\left(\frac{mL}{d_0}\right)^2 = m^2 + \left(\frac{ms}{d_0}\right)^2$$

13.1. Identification of the quantities

Let us compute each term using $d_0 = L\sqrt{1-\beta^2}$:

$$\frac{mL}{d_0} = \frac{mL}{L\sqrt{1-\beta^2}} = \frac{m}{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}} = \gamma m$$

$$\frac{ms}{d_0} = \frac{m\beta L}{L\sqrt{1-\beta^2}} = \frac{m\beta}{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}} = \gamma m\beta$$

We set:

$$E = \gamma m \quad \text{and} \quad p = \gamma m\beta$$

Hence:

$$E^2 = m^2 + p^2$$

The same Pythagorean relation as in the classical case, but with the **exact** relativistic expressions for E and p .

Figure 6 — The inertia triangle in the relativistic regime.

13.2. Comparison of the two regimes

	Classical regime	Relativistic regime
Triangle	$d^2 = L^2 + s^2$	$L^2 = d_0^2 + s^2$
L is...	a leg	the hypotenuse
Key factor	$\frac{d}{L} = \sqrt{1 + \beta^2}$	$\frac{L}{d_0} = \gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}$
E	$m\sqrt{1 + \beta^2}$	γm
p	$m\beta$	$\gamma m\beta$

14. Length contraction — the horizontal light clock

Consider now a horizontal light clock. **This device is attached to the same object as the vertical clock of section 12:** the motion coefficient β is therefore identical for both clocks and for all displacements of the device (s, s_1, s_2).

Important note: the two clocks have the same proper distance d_0 between their mirrors. The vertical distance (vertical clock, section 12) retains the value d_0 in R — it is perpendicular to the motion and is not affected by it. The horizontal distance (horizontal clock), on the other hand, is parallel to the motion: we denote ℓ its value as perceived in R , which remains to be determined. It is precisely the comparison between these two perceptions — d_0 unchanged vertically, ℓ to be determined horizontally — that will reveal length contraction.

14.1. The horizontal round trip in R

Note: the two following diagrams — *Figure 7* and *Figure 8* — represent respectively the overall motion of the rigid device (the two mirrors moving together) during the outward trip ($s_1 = \beta L_1$) and the return trip ($s_2 = \beta L_2$) of the photon.

Let ℓ denote the distance between the mirrors as perceived in R .

Figure 7 — Horizontal clock: outward trip (L_1 in R , the mirror recedes).

— On the outward trip, the front mirror recedes: $L_1 = \ell + \beta L_1$ hence $L_1 = \frac{\ell}{1 - \beta}$

Figure 8 — Horizontal clock: return trip (L_2 in R , the mirror approaches).

— On the return trip, the rear mirror approaches: $L_2 = l - \beta L_2$ hence $L_2 = \frac{l}{1 + \beta}$

The total path is:

$$L_1 + L_2 = \frac{l}{1 - \beta} + \frac{l}{1 + \beta} = \frac{2l}{1 - \beta^2}$$

14.2. Equalization with the vertical clock

The vertical clock (section 12) gives for a round trip $2L = 2\gamma d_0$. Since the two clocks have the same proper distance d_0 between their mirrors, by isotropy of light propagation in Euclidean space, they must give the same result: $L_1 + L_2 = 2L$.

Since $L = \gamma d_0$

$$2\gamma d_0 = \frac{2l}{1 - \beta^2} \quad \text{and since} \quad \frac{1}{1 - \beta^2} = \gamma^2 \quad \text{therefore} \quad \gamma d_0 = \gamma^2 l \quad \text{and:}$$

$$l = \frac{d_0}{\gamma} = d_0 \sqrt{1 - \beta^2}$$

This is **length contraction**. The argument rests solely on the isotropy of light propagation in Euclidean space.

14.3. "Time" dilation and length contraction: a single phenomenon

The preceding sections allow a unified interpretation of relativistic effects in the spatial framework. The guiding thread is the following: in all cases, **the number of cycles N is an invariant** — it is an integer count, identical in all reference frames. The only quantity that varies is **the wavelength λ** perceived by the observer.

The vertical clock (section 12): a measure of "time" dilation by the Doppler effect

In section 12.2, it was shown that in R' , the photon travels $d_0 = N\lambda'$ between the mirrors. In R , the same photon, following a longer diagonal trajectory, travels $L = N\lambda$. Since $L > d_0$ and N is constant, we necessarily have $\lambda > \lambda'$. The factor γ is written:

$$\gamma = \frac{L}{d_0} = \frac{\lambda}{\lambda'}$$

This wavelength dilation is the geometrical consequence of the diagonal lengthening, in R , of the light path in Euclidean space. The receiving mirror moves laterally away from the emission point — **this is a transverse Doppler effect**.

The horizontal clock (section 14.1): a measure of length contraction by the Doppler effect

The number of cycles N being invariant, the distances L_1 and L_2 perceived in R correspond to different wavelengths: λ_1 on the outward trip and λ_2 on the return trip.

On the outward trip, the front mirror recedes from the photon: the wavelength stretches ($\lambda_1 > \lambda$). The photon travels $L_1 = N\lambda_1$. **This is a longitudinal Doppler effect (redshift).**

On the return trip, the rear mirror approaches the photon: the wavelength compresses ($\lambda_2 < \lambda$). The photon travels $L_2 = N\lambda_2$. **This is a longitudinal Doppler effect (blueshift).**

The isotropy condition $L_1 + L_2 = 2L$ imposes $N\lambda_1 + N\lambda_2 = 2N\lambda$, hence $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 2\lambda$

Summary

What traditional physics interprets as two distinct phenomena — "time dilation" and "length contraction" — turns out to be, in the spatial framework, two manifestations of **a single phenomenon**: the modification of the wavelength of the light reference by the Doppler effect.

— The factor γ is a **dilation of λ** due to the transverse Doppler effect (vertical clock).

— Length contraction is the consequence of the **dilation-contraction of λ** due to the longitudinal Doppler effect (horizontal clock), whose exact compensation is imposed by the isotropy of light propagation in Euclidean space.

In both cases, the mechanism is purely spatial: motion modifies the light path in Euclidean space, which modifies the perceived wavelength. Time plays no part at any stage.

— See Appendix C for the experimental confirmation by the Michelson-Morley experiment —

15. The spatial transformation: change of reference frame

R' moves at β relative to R along the x axis. An event (for example a flash) is located by its position x and the light reference distance L in R , and by x' and L' in R' . We seek the relations $(x, L) \rightarrow (x', L')$.

— x : position in R of the event in space (coordinate along the direction of motion)

— L : the light reference distance in R associated with the event — the distance traveled by the wavefront since its emission.

The quantities x' and L' are the same quantities, described in the reference frame R' .

15.1. Transformation of the position: $x' = \gamma(x - \beta L)$

Figure 9 — Change of reference frame: the position x in R and x' in R' .

The diagram reads directly. The event occurs at position x in R . The reference frame R' has moved by βL relative to R . The position of the event in R' , measured from R , is therefore:

$$x - \beta L$$

But this distance is measured in R . Section 14 showed that a length measured in R is contracted by a factor γ relative to the proper length in R' . The transition from the measurement in R to the measurement in R' is therefore:

$$x' = \gamma(x - \beta L)$$

Verification: for an event located at the origin of R' ($x' = 0$), we have $x = \beta L$ — that is, the event is located exactly at the position of R' in R .

15.2. Transformation of the light reference: $L' = \gamma(L - \beta x)$

Figure 10 — Change of reference frame: the light reference L in R and L' in R' .

By symmetry with section 15.1, the diagram reads in the same way, exchanging the roles of x and L . The light reference associated with the event in R is L . The motion of R' at β induces a shift of the light reference at the position x of the event, equal to βx . The light reference of the event in R' , measured from R , is therefore:

$$L - \beta x$$

As before, this distance is measured in R and must be corrected by the factor γ to obtain the value in R' :

$$L' = \gamma(L - \beta x)$$

This expression shows that the light reference L' in R' depends on the position x of the event in R . Two events that are simultaneous in R (same L) but located at different positions ($x_1 \neq x_2$) will have different light references in R' :

$$L'_1 - L'_2 = \gamma\beta(x_2 - x_1) \neq 0$$

They are therefore not simultaneous in R' . This is the **relativity of simultaneity**, an immediate consequence of the transformation of L .

Verifications:

A photon traveling to the right satisfies $x = L$ in R . The transformation gives:

$$x' = \gamma(L - \beta L) = \gamma L(1 - \beta) \quad \text{and} \quad L' = \gamma(L - \beta L) = \gamma L(1 - \beta)$$

Hence $x' = L'$: the photon propagates at $\beta = 1$ in R' .

A photon traveling to the left satisfies $x = -L$ in R :

$$x' = \gamma(-L - \beta L) = -\gamma L(1 + \beta) \quad \text{and} \quad L' = \gamma(L + \beta L) = \gamma L(1 + \beta)$$

Hence $|x'| = L'$: the photon propagates at $\beta = 1$ in R' towards the left.

Light propagation is isotropic in R' , as in R .

15.3. The dual role of β

The two transformations $x' = \gamma(x - \beta L)$ and $L' = \gamma(L - \beta x)$ reveal a remarkable symmetry: the coefficient β plays the same role in both expressions, coupling x towards L and L towards x .

This symmetry is a direct consequence of the spatial framework: x and L are two quantities of the **same nature** — distances in Euclidean space. The coefficient β , a ratio of two lengths, operates indifferently on either one:

— βL : when the reference wavefront has traveled L , the reference frame R' has moved by βL in space.

— βx : when an event occurs at position x , the light reference of R' is shifted by βx relative to that of R .

The body measures the light and the light measures the body, reciprocally, with the same coefficient β . This reciprocity is specific to the spatial framework. In the SI framework, the Lorentz transformation involves different coefficients (v for the position, $\frac{v}{c^2}$ for the time), precisely because space (in meters) and time (in seconds) are not of the same nature.

Note: one must not confuse the relation $\lambda = \gamma\lambda'$ of section 12.2 with the transformation $L' = \gamma(L - \beta x)$. The former compares a **single physical process** (the photon of the light clock) observed from two reference frames: the number of cycles N is identical, only the wavelength changes. The latter relates the **coordinates** of a single event in two reference frames: the values L and L' do not correspond to the same count N , and no wavelength ratio can be extracted from them.

— See Appendix E for the proof —

16. Composition of velocities

Consider three reference frames R , R' and R'' aligned along the same axis. R' moves at β_1 relative to R , and R'' moves at β_2 relative to R' . What is the motion coefficient β of R'' relative to R ?

Figure 11 — Three reference frames: R' moves at β_1 relative to R , R'' at β_2 relative to R' .

16.1. Reasoning

The diagram reads directly.

The position of R'' in R' is x' . It consists of a single contribution:

— $\beta_2 L'$: the displacement of R'' relative to R' .

The position of R'' in R is x . It consists of two contributions:

— $\beta_1 L$: the displacement of R' relative to R

— $\beta_2 L'$: the displacement of R'' relative to R'

In classical mechanics ($\beta \ll 1$), $L' \approx L$, and the position in R would simply be $x \approx \beta_1 L + \beta_2 L = (\beta_1 + \beta_2)L$, hence $\beta = \beta_1 + \beta_2$. This is the Galilean addition of velocities.

But section 14 showed that the light reference is not the same in R and R' : $L' \neq L$. The displacement $\beta_2 L'$ cannot therefore be directly added to $\beta_1 L$. One must first express L' in terms of the quantities of R .

The spatial transformation (section 15) gives:

$$x' = \gamma_1(x - \beta_1 L) \text{ and } L' = \gamma_1(L - \beta_1 x)$$

Now in R' , $0 = \gamma_2(x' - \beta_2 L')$ \Rightarrow $x' = \beta_2 L'$ Therefore, by identification of x' and L' :

$$\gamma_1(x - \beta_1 L) = \beta_2 \gamma_1(L - \beta_1 x) \Rightarrow x - \beta_1 L = \beta_2 L - \beta_1 \beta_2 x \Rightarrow x(1 + \beta_1 \beta_2) = L(\beta_1 + \beta_2)$$

The motion coefficient R'' in R is $\beta = \frac{x}{L}$, hence:

$$\beta = \frac{\beta_1 + \beta_2}{1 + \beta_1 \beta_2}$$

The term $\beta_1 \beta_2$ in the denominator is the correction that prevents velocities from adding simply. It arises directly from the fact that $L' \neq L$ — that is, from the difference in perception of the light reference between the two reference frames R' and R .

16.2. Verifications

Classical case ($\beta_1, \beta_2 \ll 1$): the product $\beta_1\beta_2$ is negligible compared to 1, and $\beta \approx \beta_1 + \beta_2$. We recover the classical addition of velocities.

Two photons ($\beta_1 = 1, \beta_2 = 1$): $\beta = 1$. The composition of two light velocities gives the speed of light — not double.

Object + light ($\beta_2 = 1, \beta_1$ arbitrary): $\beta = \frac{\beta_1 + 1}{1 + \beta_1} = 1$. Whatever the reference frame, light remains at $\beta = 1$.

This last result confirms that the constancy of $\beta = 1$ for light in all reference frames is not a postulate: it is a **demonstrated consequence** of the spatial transformation, itself derived from the isotropy of Euclidean space and length contraction.

Two material objects ($\beta_1 < 1, \beta_2 < 1$): the numerator $\beta_1 + \beta_2$ is always smaller than the denominator $1 + \beta_1\beta_2$, hence $\beta < 1$. Two composed material objects always give a material object — never a photon.

17. $E = mc^2$ as a unit conversion

In the spatial framework, the total mass-energy at rest is simply:

$$E = \gamma m = m \quad (\text{when } \beta = 0)$$

It is a mass, in kilograms. To recover the energy in SI units:

$$E_{\text{SI}} = E c^2 = m c^2$$

The relation $E = mc^2$ is a **unit conversion** between the kilogram (natural unit of energy in the spatial framework) and the joule (a unit that incorporates the second). The factor c^2 plays the same role as the factor **1000** between the meter and the kilometer: it relates two measurement scales of the same physical quantity.

18. The limit $\beta < 1$: a logical exclusion

18.1. Three distinct arguments

Traditional physics justifies the impossibility for a material body to reach the speed of light — that is, $\beta = 1$ — by a dynamical argument: the energy $E = \gamma m$ diverges as $\beta \rightarrow 1$, so infinite energy would be required. This argument is correct, but it presents the limit as a wall that cannot be crossed for lack of means — not as an impossibility of principle.

The spatial framework allows three arguments of different nature to be distinguished, in order of increasing importance.

Geometrical argument. The coefficient $\beta = \frac{ds}{dl}$ is the ratio between the distance traveled by the object and the distance traveled simultaneously by the light reference. To say that $\beta \geq 1$ would amount to saying that the object travels a distance at least as great as the ruler that measures it. This is a limit inherent to the very definition of measurement, not a dynamical constraint imposed on matter.

Invariance argument. Section 16 demonstrated that the composition of velocities is written $\beta = \frac{\beta_1 + \beta_2}{1 + \beta_1\beta_2}$. This law possesses a remarkable property: if $\beta_2 = 1$, then $\beta = 1$ whatever β_1 . The value $\beta = 1$ is a fixed point of the composition — it is invariant under change of reference frame. No other value of β possesses this property. A material object at $\beta = 1$ in one reference frame would be at $\beta = 1$ in all reference frames.

Information argument. Light plays a dual role in the spatial framework: — it is the measurement reference ($L = N\lambda$); — it is the vehicle of all physical information.

This duality is decisive. If one chose sound as a reference, a supersonic object would escape acoustic measurement — but would remain observable by light. The limit would be formal, not physical. Light is the ultimate case: an object at $\beta = 1$ would escape not only measurement, but all observation and all causal interaction. No information about it could reach any observer.

— See Appendix F for the statement and formal proof of this result —

18.2. The logical exclusion

The combination of the three arguments leads to a conclusion stronger than a mere practical impossibility.

A material object reaching $\beta = 1$:

- would reach $\beta = 1$ in all reference frames (invariance);
- could not transmit any information to any observer (reference/information duality);
- would therefore cease to exist physically for all observers.

Yet an object that exists for no observer is not a physical object. The inequality $\beta < 1$ for matter is therefore not a limit that one approaches without ever reaching: it is a logical exclusion, imposed by the very nature of measurement and information in Euclidean space.

Figure 12 — The spatial diagram (s, L): the boundary $\beta = 1$ separates the domain of matter from the forbidden domain.

18.3. The photon: a case apart

The photon exists at $\beta = 1$ — but it is not a counterexample. The photon has no proper reference frame: one cannot "place oneself in the reference frame of the photon" and observe physics from there. The photon is the reference itself. Its mass is zero, its energy equals its momentum ($E = p$), and the totality of its inertia is engaged in motion, with no rest component.

The photon does not cross the limit $\beta = 1$ from $\beta < 1$: it is born and dies at $\beta = 1$. The distinction between matter ($\beta < 1$ strictly) and light ($\beta = 1$ exactly) is not a difference of degree — it is a difference of nature.

Summary table

The table below summarizes the correspondence between SI quantities and spatial framework quantities, illustrating the dimensional convergence.

Quantity	SI symbol	SI unit	Spatial symbol	Spatial unit	SI conversion
Reference variable	t	s	L	m	$t = \frac{L}{c}$
Velocity	v	$m s^{-1}$	β	—	$v = \beta \times c$
Gravitational constant	G_{SI}	$m^3 kg^{-1} s^{-2}$	G	$m kg^{-1}$	$G_{SI} = G \times c^2$
Acceleration	a_{SI}	$m s^{-2}$	a	m^{-1}	$a_{SI} = a \times c^2$
Force	F_{SI}	$kg m s^{-2}$	F	$kg m^{-1}$	$F_{SI} = F \times c^2$
Momentum	p_{SI}	$kg m s^{-1}$	p	kg	$p_{SI} = p \times c$
Kinetic energy	Ek_{SI}	$kg m^2 s^{-2}$	Ek	kg	$Ek_{SI} = Ek \times c^2$
Work	W_{SI}		W		$W_{SI} = W \times c^2$
Total energy Mass-energy	E_{SI}		E		$E_{SI} = E \times c^2$

The table above illustrates a fact whose significance goes beyond the mere dimensional convergence of mechanics: a system of units is never a neutral choice of representation. By multiplying the fundamental units, it can fragment into seemingly distinct quantities what shares the same physical property. Mass, momentum and kinetic energy, separated by the powers of c in the SI framework, turn out in the spatial framework to be three manifestations of a single quantity — inertia — all measurable in kilograms.

This observation has an important epistemological consequence. A mathematical model, however rigorous and predictive, is no guarantee of a correct interpretation of physical reality: what its equations bring to light depends on the system of units in which they are written. A unified structure can remain invisible behind a dimensional fragmentation; conversely, two seemingly related quantities can turn out to be of distinct natures once the units are correctly chosen. The general conclusion returns to this point, extending the analysis to the full set of seven SI base units.

A vertical reading of the "Unit" column of the spatial framework reveals the convergence: the SI units (s, m, kg) reduce to **two fundamental units** — the **meter (m)** for distances and the reference, and the **kilogram (kg)** for all quantities related to inertia. The motion coefficient β , a pure dimensionless number, replaces the velocity of the SI framework. The factors c and c^2 are merely conversions between these natural units and the SI units.

General conclusion

A. What has been established

This work has shown that physics — classical and relativistic — can be entirely reformulated within a purely spatial framework, without recourse to the temporal variable.

The systematic replacement of the variable t by the light reference distance $L = N\lambda$ leads to a framework in which:

— velocity becomes a pure dimensionless number, the motion coefficient $\beta = \frac{ds}{dL}$, a ratio of two distances in Euclidean space;

— mass, momentum and energy converge to the same unit (the kilogram), revealing that they are three manifestations of inertia;

— the relation $E^2 = m^2 + p^2$ follows from the Pythagorean theorem in Euclidean space, both in the classical and relativistic regimes — the transition between the two reducing to an inversion of the role of L in the fundamental triangle: leg in the classical case ($d^2 = L^2 + s^2$), hypotenuse in the relativistic case ($L^2 = d_0^2 + s^2$);

— the factor $\gamma = \frac{L}{d_0} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}}$ is a ratio of distances in ordinary space;

— "time dilation" and "length contraction" are two manifestations of a single phenomenon: the modification of the wavelength of the light reference by the Doppler effect — transverse for γ (vertical clock), longitudinal for the contraction (horizontal clock);

— the spatial transformation $x' = \gamma(x - \beta L)$, $L' = \gamma(L - \beta x)$ and the relativistic composition of velocities $\beta = \frac{\beta_1 + \beta_2}{1 + \beta_1 \beta_2}$ are deduced from the isotropy of light propagation in Euclidean space and the length contraction that follows from it (see Appendix E);

— the case of the photon ($m = 0$) fits naturally within this framework: $E^2 = p^2$, hence $E = p$ — energy and momentum are equal (both in kilograms), and $\beta = 1$ exactly. The photon is the object for which the totality of inertia is engaged in motion, with no rest component.

All of these results follow from two fundamental properties of Euclidean space — its homogeneity and its isotropy — and from the principle of relativity, which requires that these properties hold in every inertial reference frame. The whole of special relativity is contained therein.

The numerical results of established physics are fully preserved — not a single prediction changes.

B. What the spatial framework brings

What changes is understanding.

Spatial acceleration and its characteristic length. The quantity $\frac{1}{a_t}$, the inverse of the tangential component of the spatial acceleration, receives a direct physical interpretation: it is the distance the light wavefront must travel for the object to reach $\beta = 1$. For terrestrial gravity, $\frac{1}{g} \approx 0.97$ light-year — revealing the extreme weakness of terrestrial gravity at the cosmic scale, invisible in the classical value $g \approx 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$.

$E = mc^2$ as a unit conversion. In the spatial framework, the rest energy is simply $E = m$, in kilograms. The relation $E = mc^2$ does not express a deep equivalence between mass and energy: it expresses a change of unit between the kilogram (natural unit) and the joule (a unit that incorporates the second). The factor c^2 plays the same role as the factor **1000** between the meter and the kilometer.

Distinction from the convention $c = 1$. In particle physics, it is common to set $c = 1$ by convention, which renders velocity dimensionless and unifies the units of mass, momentum and energy. The dimensional convergence obtained in the spatial framework might appear identical to this convention. It differs in nature and in scope. The convention $c = 1$ is a notational choice: it simplifies the expressions but retains time as a fundamental variable — the equations of motion remain parametrized by t , and the second remains implicitly present in the structure of the formalism. The spatial framework eliminates the temporal variable itself. The dimensional convergence does not result from a choice of units but from the removal of the

quantity that fragmented the units. The factors c and c^2 are not "set equal to 1" — they disappear because the second, which generated them, no longer exists. The distinction is that between simplifying an expression and identifying the source of its complexity.

The simplified energy-momentum four-vector. The energy-momentum four-vector of special relativity, $\mathbf{P} = \left(\frac{E}{c}, \mathbf{p}_x, \mathbf{p}_y, \mathbf{p}_z\right)$, groups four quantities made homogeneous by the factor $\frac{1}{c}$. In the spatial framework, this homogenization is unnecessary: E and \mathbf{p} already have the same dimension (\mathbf{kg}). The four-vector reduces to $(E, \mathbf{p}_x, \mathbf{p}_y, \mathbf{p}_z)$, and its invariant $E^2 - \mathbf{p}^2 = m^2$ is none other than the Pythagorean theorem applied to the inertia triangle.

Let us note that in the spatial framework, this mathematical object and its invariant are not reserved for the relativistic domain: they are already established in the classical regime (section 7), as soon as the inertia triangle is constructed. The transition to the relativistic regime does not modify the structure — it merely replaces the approximate expressions of E and \mathbf{p} by their exact expressions. A concept usually considered as exclusively relativistic thus becomes accessible from classical mechanics onward.

The spatial invariant and the Minkowski metric. The relation $L^2 = \mathbf{d}_0^2 + \mathbf{s}^2$, established in section 12, can be rewritten $\mathbf{d}_0^2 = L^2 - \mathbf{s}^2$ — where all three quantities are distances in Euclidean space. This expression is mathematically isomorphic to the Minkowski interval $d\mathbf{s}^2 = c^2 dt^2 - d\mathbf{x}^2$, but with a decisive difference of interpretation: the invariant is no longer proper time — an abstract quantity, not directly measurable as a length — but the proper distance \mathbf{d}_0 , a measurable Euclidean quantity. The Minkowski metric is not invoked as a foundation: it emerges as a geometrical by-product of the spatial framework. The pseudo-Euclidean four-dimensional space, with its signature $(-, +, +, +)$, turns out to be a reformulation — in a language mixing space and time — of a purely spatial three-dimensional geometry.

Einstein's postulate as a consequence. The spatial framework does not postulate any speed limit. The constancy of $\beta = 1$ for light in all reference frames is a demonstrated consequence of the spatial transformation (section 15.2) and of the composition of velocities (section 16.2) — see also Appendix D. What Einstein posited as an axiom in 1905 appears here as a theorem.

The symmetry of the coefficient β . In the spatial transformation, β couples \mathbf{x} towards L and L towards \mathbf{x} with the same coefficient — **the body measures the light and the light measures the body**, reciprocally. Appendix E demonstrates that this symmetry is a necessary consequence of the isotropy of light propagation. In the SI framework, this symmetry is masked by the heterogeneity of the units (\mathbf{v} for the position, $\frac{\mathbf{v}}{c^2}$ for the time).

$\beta < 1$: a logical exclusion. Section 18 establishes that the limit $\beta < 1$ for any material object does not result from a dynamical obstacle — the infinite energy required to reach $\beta = 1$ — but from a logical exclusion, imposed by the very nature of measurement and information in Euclidean space.

Nothing is replaced. Everything is re-read. And this re-reading, simpler, more geometrical, more direct, is made possible by a single choice: replacing the temporal variable by a pure spatial variable.

C. Scope, limitations and perspectives

Space as a physical entity. The coefficient $\beta = \frac{d\mathbf{s}}{dL}$, the foundation of the entire spatial framework, couples two distances of the same nature: the displacement of matter ($d\mathbf{s}$) and the progression of the light reference (dL). The absolute isotropy of this propagation — verified in all reference frames, confirmed by the Michelson-Morley experiment — shows that space is not an empty and passive container. It is a physical entity endowed with measurable properties, of which electromagnetic propagation is the direct expression. And it is these properties — homogeneity and isotropy — which, combined with the principle of relativity, underpin all of the physics developed in this work.

Implications for the unit system. The dimensional convergence brought to light in this work — mass, momentum, kinetic energy, work, all expressed in kilograms — is not an artifact of the spatial framework: it reveals that the SI system, by introducing the second as an independent fundamental unit, fragments into apparently distinct quantities what are in fact manifestations of a single physical property: inertia. The factors c and c^2 that clutter classical relations are merely the traces of this fragmentation. The analysis can be pushed further. For mechanics, the elimination of the second reduces the system to two fundamental units: the **meter** and the **kilogram**, which covers everything related to inertia (mass, momentum, energy, work). Velocity, having become the motion coefficient β , is a pure dimensionless number. When electromagnetism

is included, a third irreducible unit appears: the **coulomb**, the only quantity that cannot be reduced to the previous two. The mole is a pure number; the candela is a derived quantity. The seven SI base units reduce to three.

A word for the kelvin and Boltzmann. The case of the kelvin, and of the Boltzmann constant that relates it to energy, nevertheless deserves special treatment. The relation $\langle \varepsilon \rangle = \frac{1}{2} k_B T$ — where $\langle \varepsilon \rangle$ denotes the average kinetic energy per particle and per degree of freedom — shows that temperature is, up to a coefficient, a kinetic energy. To measure a temperature is to measure the average kinetic energy of thermal agitation per particle, expressed in kilograms in the spatial framework or in joules in the SI framework.

- **The kelvin is therefore not a fundamental unit.** Temperature is an intensive, statistical quantity, defined for an ensemble of particles and not for an isolated particle; but through the relation $\langle \varepsilon \rangle = \frac{1}{2} k_B T$, measuring a temperature amounts to measuring the average kinetic energy per particle and per degree of freedom. The kelvin is thus a macroscopic measure of a microscopic energy.
- **The constant k_B converts temperature, expressed in kelvins, into energy**, expressed in kilograms (spatial framework) or in joules (SI framework). The passage from the spatial framework to the SI framework is written $k_{B,SI} = k_B \times c^2$, that is $k_B \approx 1.54 \times 10^{-40} \text{ kg K}^{-1}$. Read as a unit-conversion factor, within the spatial framework, this value directly gives the equivalence:

$$1 \text{ K} \leftrightarrow 1.54 \times 10^{-40} \text{ kg}$$

exactly as the value of c gives:

$$1 \text{ s} \leftrightarrow 3 \times 10^8 \text{ m}$$

But unlike c , which is a conversion factor between frameworks (SI \leftrightarrow spatial) and disappears within the spatial framework itself, k_B cannot be eliminated. It does not reflect a historical fragmentation of units, but the relation between two physically distinct levels of description: the microscopic statistical description (average kinetic energy per particle) and the macroscopic thermodynamic description (temperature as observed by a thermometer). This relation is a property of nature, present in both frameworks and irreducible.

The seven SI base units thus reduce to three fundamental units — the meter, the kilogram, and the coulomb — to which is added a scale-conversion factor, k_B , irreducible regardless of the dimensional framework.

The challenge of gravity. The present work covers the spatial reformulation of classical mechanics and special relativity — that is, physics in flat space. In this domain, the spatial framework is complete and exact: it reproduces all predictions of standard physics without any additional approximation.

Two elements of the spatial framework suggest entry points towards general relativity:

— The universality of spatial gravitational acceleration: because mass cancels in $\mathbf{g} = \frac{GM}{r^2}$, this quantity depends only on the position in space and on the source mass M , not on the accelerated object. In the spatial framework, this reads directly: the variation of the motion coefficient per unit light reference distance is a local property of space, identical for all objects. This universality — which is, in the temporal framework, the equivalent of the equivalence principle — permits (without requiring) a geometrical interpretation of gravity. The spatial framework suggests a specific form of this interpretation: the geometry would not reside in spacetime itself, but in the light reference — whose wavelength λ would vary from one point to another in the gravitational field, exactly as it varies with motion in the relativistic regime (see Appendix G).

— The term $N d\lambda$: the transition between the classical and relativistic regimes hinges on the variation of the perceived wavelength. In gravitation, the gravitational redshift is precisely such a variation. The formulation $L = N\lambda$ offers a natural entry point for addressing this question.

It would be of interest to explore general relativity, with all its challenges, within the spatial framework. This exploration constitutes the natural continuation of the present work.

Appendices

Appendix A. Kinematics example: free fall

Statement

A body is released from rest at a height $h = 1000 \text{ m}$. Let us describe its motion in the spatial framework and verify consistency with the SI framework.

Data in SI units

$$h = 1000 \text{ m} , \quad v_0 = 0 \text{ m.s}^{-1} , \quad g_{SI} \approx 9.81 \text{ m.s}^{-2} , \quad c \approx 299792458 \text{ m.s}^{-1}.$$

Conversion to the spatial framework

The initial coefficient β and the spatial acceleration:

$$\beta_0 = \frac{v_0}{c} = 0 , \quad g \approx 1.09 \times 10^{-16} \text{ m}^{-1}$$

Solution in the spatial framework

The equations of motion with $z_0 = 0$ and $\beta_0 = 0$ are :

$$z(L) = g \frac{L^2}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta(L) = gL$$

The ground is reached when $z = h$:

$$L_{\text{impact}} = \sqrt{\frac{2h}{g}} \approx \sqrt{\frac{2 \times 1000}{1.09 \times 10^{-16}}} \approx 4.28 \times 10^9 \text{ m}$$

The coefficient β at impact:

$$\beta_{\text{impact}} = g \times L_{\text{impact}} \approx 1.09 \times 10^{-16} \times 4.28 \times 10^9 \approx 4.67 \times 10^{-7}$$

Back-conversion to SI units

The classical duration:

$$t_{\text{impact}} = \frac{L_{\text{impact}}}{c} \approx \frac{4.28 \times 10^9}{299792458} \approx 14.3 \text{ s}$$

The classical velocity:

$$v_{\text{impact}} = \beta_{\text{impact}} \times c \approx 4.67 \times 10^{-7} \times 299792458 \approx 140 \text{ m.s}^{-1}.$$

These values are identical to those obtained classically. The reformulation is consistent.

The smallness of $\beta_{\text{impact}} \approx 4.67 \times 10^{-7}$ directly expresses that the body moves at a minute velocity compared to the measuring ruler — the signature of a non-relativistic regime.

Appendix B. The gravitational case

Setting $G = \frac{G_{SI}}{c^2}$, the universal gravitational constant in the spatial framework, the gravitational force $F = mg$ exerted on an object of mass m by a body of mass M is written $F = \frac{GMm}{r^2}$. The corresponding spatial acceleration is:

$$g = \frac{F}{m} = \frac{GM}{r^2}$$

The mass m of the object cancels out: the spatial gravitational acceleration depends only on the position in space and on the source mass M , not on the accelerated object. This universality, a direct consequence of the proportionality of the gravitational force to mass, permits (without requiring) a geometrical interpretation of gravity.

The formal expression is identical to that of the SI framework. The dimension of \mathbf{G} is $m \cdot kg^{-1}$: it relates the source mass to the spatial acceleration it generates in the surrounding space.

Within the present work, the quantity $\mathbf{g} = \frac{F}{m} = \frac{d\beta}{dL}$ measures the variation of the motion coefficient per unit light reference distance. Its inverse $\frac{1}{\mathbf{g}} = \frac{dL}{d\beta}$ is the **distance that the light wavefront must travel for the object to reach $\beta = 1$: a characteristic length, traveled by the light reference**, of the intensity of the gravitational acceleration experienced by the body.

Appendix C. Experimental confirmation: the Michelson-Morley experiment (1887)

The Michelson-Morley interferometer is the exact physical realization of the comparison between the vertical and horizontal clocks of section 14. Two light beams travel round trips along two perpendicular arms, then are recombined. If the round trips differ ($L_1 + L_2 \neq 2L$), interference fringes shift when the apparatus is rotated.

Experimental result: no fringe shift was observed, regardless of orientation. This directly confirms that:

$$\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 2\lambda$$

In the spatial framework, this result is unsurprising: it is a geometrical property of the Doppler effect in an isotropic Euclidean space, demonstrated in section 14.3.

The Michelson-Morley interferometer is, in the spatial framework, the exact physical realization of the device used in this work: **two perpendicular light clocks**. One arm corresponds to the vertical clock of section 11 (**round trip** = $2L$), the other to the horizontal clock of section 14 (**round trip** = $L_1 + L_2$). The absence of interference fringes directly confirms that $L_1 + L_2 = 2L$ — the isotropy condition that underpins length contraction.

In 1887, Michelson and Morley were searching for an aether — a material medium through which light would propagate. They found none. In the spatial framework, their result has a simple interpretation: light does not need a medium because it is a manifestation of isotropic Euclidean space itself. What they measured, without knowing it, was the isotropy of light propagation in Euclidean space.

Appendix D. Additional argument for the choice of the light reference

Section 3 justified the choice of electromagnetic propagation as a reference on **four grounds**. **The Michelson-Morley experiment provides a fifth**.

The relation $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 2\lambda$, required for the consistency of the spatial framework and for length contraction, holds only if the isotropy of propagation in Euclidean space is **absolute** — that is, independent of the reference frame of observation. This is a property of space itself, not of a material medium.

Any propagation tied to a material medium satisfies this isotropy only in the rest frame of the medium, and loses it in every other frame. Light is the only propagation whose isotropy is a property of Euclidean space itself, confirmed experimentally by the absence of fringes in the Michelson-Morley experiment.

Note on Einstein's postulate

In 1905, Einstein postulated that the speed of light is the same in all reference frames. From this postulate, he deduced the whole of special relativity.

The spatial framework does not postulate any speed limit. The limit $\beta < 1$ is a logical consequence of the choice of electromagnetic propagation as a reference: an object cannot travel a greater distance than the ruler that measures it. The numerical value **1** results from the fact that this reference is the fastest propagation in space and is used as the vehicle of information.

Einstein's postulate decomposes, in the spatial framework, into two more fundamental elements: the local isotropy of light propagation — an experimental fact confirmed by the Michelson-Morley experiment — and the principle of relativity, which requires that this isotropy hold in every inertial reference frame. These two elements underpin the spatial transformation (Appendix E). Section 16.2 then demonstrates a specific consequence: $\beta = 1$ is a fixed point of velocity composition — whatever the reference frame, light remains at $\beta = 1$. It is this property that the spatial framework establishes as a theorem — a statement of which is proposed in Appendix F — where Einstein posited it as an axiom.

Let us note that the isotropy established by the Michelson-Morley experiment is a round-trip isotropy — the only one accessible to measurement without a convention for synchronizing distant clocks. The spatial framework is built exclusively on such round-trip comparisons (sections 12 and 14), without any hypothesis on the one-way speed of light.

Appendix E. Proof of the $x \leftrightarrow L$ symmetry

Section 15.3 observes that the coefficient β plays the same role in both transformations $x' = \gamma(x - \beta L)$ and $L' = \gamma(L - \beta x)$, coupling x towards L and L towards x . This symmetry is a necessary consequence of the isotropy of light propagation in Euclidean space.

Step 1 — Homogeneity of space and linearity

The reference frames R and R' considered here are Galilean (inertial), that is, in uniform rectilinear motion relative to each other. The homogeneity of Euclidean space — the fact that its physical properties are identical at every point — combined with this inertial character, requires that the transformation between R and R' be linear. Were it to depend on the point in space, two observers located at different positions would obtain different transformations, contradicting the uniformity of space. This condition eliminates any non-linear transformation and reduces the problem to the determination of four constant coefficients. Let us therefore start from the most general form of a linear transformation between the coordinates (x, L) in R and (x', L') in R' :

$$x' = Ax + BL$$

$$L' = Cx + DL$$

where A, B, C, D are four coefficients to be determined. We impose four purely spatial conditions.

Step 2 — Isotropy of light propagation

The isotropy of light propagation in Euclidean space is an experimental fact, confirmed in particular by the Michelson-Morley experiment (Appendix C). The principle of relativity — the laws of physics are the same in all inertial reference frames — requires that this local isotropy, verified experimentally in a given reference frame, hold identically in every inertial reference frame. A photon therefore propagates at $\beta = 1$ in R and in R' .

A photon propagating to the right satisfies $x = L$ in R and must satisfy $x' = L'$ in R' :

$$(1) \quad A + B = C + D$$

A photon propagating to the left satisfies $x = -L$ in R and must satisfy $x' = -L'$ in R' :

$$(2) \quad A - B = D - C$$

Adding (1) and (2): $A = D$. Subtracting (2) from (1): $B = C$.

The transformation therefore necessarily takes the form:

$$x' = Ax + BL$$

$$L' = Bx + AL$$

The coefficients of x and L are exchanged between the two equations. The $x \leftrightarrow L$ symmetry is proved: it follows from the isotropy of light propagation in Euclidean space alone.

Step 3 — Motion of R' , origin condition

The origin of R' ($x' = 0$) moves at β in R , that is $x = \beta L$:

$$0 = A(\beta L) + BL \Rightarrow B = -A\beta$$

Hence:

$$x' = A(x - \beta L)$$

$$L' = A(L - \beta x)$$

Step 4 — Length contraction

Section 14 established that a length measured in R is contracted by a factor γ relative to its proper value in R' . This result requires:

$$A = \gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}$$

We recover the complete spatial transformation:

$$\begin{aligned}x' &= \gamma(x - \beta L) \\L' &= \gamma(L - \beta x)\end{aligned}$$

Summary

The spatial transformation is entirely determined by four conditions:

1. Linearity (homogeneity of space)
2. Isotropy — photon to the right, photon to the left
3. Motion of R' at β
4. Length contraction

All are of a purely spatial nature. The symmetry between x and L , far from being a remarkable property observed a posteriori, is the first consequence of isotropy, obtained as early as step 2.

Remark: this proof works in this form only because x and L are of the same nature — distances in Euclidean space. In the SI framework, the same isotropy conditions apply with ct in place of L and produce the same algebraic relations, but the factor $\frac{1}{c}$ breaks the symmetry when one reverts to the variable t .

Appendix F. Invariance theorem for $\beta = 1$

Preamble: the logical chain and the absence of circularity

The following theorem establishes that $\beta = 1$ is the unique fixed point of the law of composition of motion coefficients. This result might appear circular: the construction of the spatial framework uses the isotropy of light propagation, and the theorem concludes that $\beta = 1$ is invariant — does one simply recover at the output what was put in at the input?

The answer is no, and it is essential to show this in detail.

The input of the construction is a local experimental fact: light propagation isotropic in Euclidean space, independently of the reference frame. This fact is established by the Michelson-Morley experiment (Appendix C), which measures a round-trip property of light at a given point.

The determination of the factor γ (section 12) does not use Einstein's postulate that the speed of light is the same in all reference frames. It rests on three elements of different nature:

1. **A choice of reference.** The variable $L = N\lambda$ is defined as the distance traveled by the electromagnetic wavefront. To say that the photon of the light clock travels the distance L when the light reference travels L is a tautology — the standard meter measures one meter. This is not a physical postulate: it is the very definition of the reference variable.
2. **Experimental isotropy.** Light propagation occurs isotropically in Euclidean space — in particular, the wavefront propagates perpendicularly to the motion as well as parallel to it. This fact, confirmed by the Michelson-Morley experiment, authorizes the construction of the vertical light clock and the formation of the relativistic fundamental triangle.
3. **The Pythagorean theorem.** Euclidean geometry applies to the triangle formed by d_0 (proper distance between the mirrors), s (displacement of the object) and L (diagonal path of the photon). The relation $L^2 = d_0^2 + s^2$ is a consequence of this geometry, and the factor $\gamma = \frac{L}{d_0} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}}$ follows directly.

From γ , length contraction is demonstrated by the equalization of the vertical and horizontal clocks (section 14), using exclusively the isotropy of light propagation. The spatial transformation is then demonstrated in Appendix E from linearity (homogeneity of space), isotropy (photon to the right, photon to the left), the motion of R' at β , and length contraction. The law of composition of velocities (section 16) is finally deduced from this transformation.

The complete logical chain is therefore:

Local isotropy (experimental fact) \rightarrow fundamental triangle and γ (Euclidean geometry) \rightarrow length contraction (isotropy) \rightarrow spatial transformation (Appendix E) \rightarrow composition law (section 16) \rightarrow invariance theorem (below)

Each step adds a new result. The input is a local round-trip measurement; the output is a global property of the composition law, valid in all reference frames. The invariance of $\beta = 1$ for light — which Einstein posited as an axiom in 1905 — appears here as a theorem, demonstrated from Euclidean geometry and the isotropy of light propagation.

The law of composition of motion coefficients, demonstrated in section 16, which is written $\beta = \frac{\beta_1 + \beta_2}{1 + \beta_1 \beta_2}$, naturally leads to the following theorem.

Invariance theorem for $\beta = 1$. The value $\beta = 1$ is the unique fixed point of the law of composition of motion coefficients:

- if $\beta_2 = 1$, then $\beta = 1$ whatever β_1 ;
- if $\beta_1 < 1$ and $\beta_2 < 1$, then $\beta < 1$.

The boundary $\beta = 1$ is invariant under change of reference frame and cannot be crossed by composition of material motions.

Proof.

(i) *Fixed point.* If $\beta_2 = 1$:

$$\beta = \frac{\beta_1 + 1}{1 + \beta_1} = 1, \text{ whatever } \beta_1.$$

(ii) *Closure of the material domain.* If $0 \leq \beta_1 < 1$ and $0 \leq \beta_2 < 1$:

the numerator $\beta_1 + \beta_2$ is strictly less than the denominator $1 + \beta_1 \beta_2$, hence $\beta < 1$.

(iii) *Uniqueness.* Let us seek β_0 such that the composition of β_0 with any β_1 yields β_0 :

$$\frac{\beta_1 + \beta_0}{1 + \beta_1 \beta_0} = \beta_0 \text{ for all } \beta_1.$$

This requires $\beta_1(1 - \beta_0^2) = 0$ for all β_1 , hence $\beta_0 = 1$. No other value possesses this property.

This theorem expresses, in the spatial framework, what Einstein postulated in 1905: the constancy of the speed of light in all reference frames. The difference is that this property is no longer an axiom — it follows from the composition law, itself deduced from the isotropy of light propagation in homogeneous Euclidean space and the principle of relativity (Appendix E).

Note: points (i) and (iii) of this theorem underpin the invariance argument of section 18.1. Point (ii) establishes that the domain $\beta < 1$ is closed under composition — a result that enters into the logical exclusion developed in section 18.2.

Appendix G. The equivalence principle in the spatial framework

In Newtonian mechanics, mass appears in two physically distinct roles. The inertial mass m_i enters Newton's second law ($F = m_i a$): it measures the resistance of an object to change of motion. The gravitational mass m_g enters the law of gravitation ($F = \frac{G M m_g}{r^2}$): it measures how an object responds to the gravitational field created by a source mass M . It is the "mass charge" — analogous to the electric charge q that measures the response to the electric field.

A priori, nothing relates these two quantities. The electric charge, for instance, bears no relation to the inertial mass: a proton and an electron have the same charge (in absolute value) but radically different inertial masses, and respond differently to the electric field. One could likewise conceive that two objects with the same gravitational mass respond differently to the gravitational field. Yet this is never what is observed: the gravitational mass is always exactly equal to the inertial mass.

The consequence is immediate. The equation of motion in a gravitational field, $m_i \mathbf{a} = \frac{GMm_g}{r^2}$, simplifies to $\mathbf{a} = \frac{GM}{r^2}$.

Acceleration no longer depends on the object. All bodies fall in the same way. This is the weak equivalence principle.

Einstein's interpretation. If all bodies undergo the same acceleration at a given point, then this acceleration is not a property of the bodies — it is a property of spacetime at that point. And if it is a property of spacetime, then gravity is not a "force" — it is geometry. A body in free fall follows the curvature of spacetime without experiencing any force. This is the foundation of general relativity.

The reading in the spatial framework. The simplification gives $\mathbf{a} = \frac{GM}{r^2}$, that is, $\frac{d\beta}{dL} = \frac{GM}{r^2}$. This quantity is the variation of the motion coefficient per unit light reference distance, at a point in space. It depends only on M and r . It is identical for all objects.

The reading is subtly different from Einstein's. In the spatial framework, this result says: the relation between the light reference and the motion of matter is universal — it is the same for all objects at a given point. It is not necessarily spacetime that is "curved" — it is the light reference that varies with position.

If the wavelength λ varies from one point to another in the gravitational field — which the gravitational redshift confirms experimentally — then the reference $L = N\lambda$ is no longer the same everywhere. The analogy is that of refraction: in a medium with variable refractive index, light follows curved paths in a flat space. If light serves as the reference for measuring trajectories, one perceives curvature — but the underlying space remains Euclidean.

The open question is how far this analogy can be pushed: can all gravitational effects — light deflection, Shapiro delay, perihelion precession, gravitational waves — be accounted for in a Euclidean space endowed with a light reference of variable wavelength, or is the curvature of spacetime irreducible? The exploration of this question constitutes the natural continuation of the present work.

Appendix H. Mass invariance and Newton's second law

Newton's second law, in its most general form, is written:

$$\vec{F} = \frac{d\vec{p}}{dL}$$

This expression, though mathematically correct, is physically misleading: it suggests that the variation of momentum could arise from a variation of mass. This is never the case. The mass m is an intrinsic property of the object, invariant in both the classical and relativistic regimes, whether the framework is temporal or spatial.

The classical regime

In the classical regime, $\vec{p} = m\vec{\beta}$. The mass being constant: $d\vec{p} = m d\vec{\beta}$

The fundamental law is written:

$$\vec{F} = m \frac{d\vec{\beta}}{dL} = m\vec{a}$$

Force acts on mass and modifies the motion coefficient $\vec{\beta}$ — in magnitude and/or in direction. The mass m measures the resistance to this modification.

The relativistic regime

In the relativistic regime, $\vec{p} = \gamma m \vec{\beta}$. The mass being constant:

$$d\vec{p} = m d(\gamma \vec{\beta})$$

The fundamental law is written:

$$\vec{F} = m \frac{d(\gamma \vec{\beta})}{dL}$$

What varies is not the mass, but the product $\gamma \vec{\beta}$ — the motion coefficient corrected by the geometrical factor $\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}}$, arising from the Pythagorean theorem applied to the relativistic fundamental triangle (section 12).

From relativistic to classical

The classical regime is defined by $\beta \ll 1$. In this limit, $\gamma \approx 1$ and $d(\gamma \vec{\beta}) \approx d\vec{\beta}$.

The relativistic expression:

$$\vec{F} = m \frac{d(\gamma \vec{\beta})}{dL}$$

reduces to:

$$\vec{F} = m \frac{d\vec{\beta}}{dL} = m \vec{a}$$

The classical regime is contained in the relativistic regime as a limiting case.